

Neoliberalism and Global Textbooks: A Critical Ethnography of English language classrooms in Serbia¹

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Abstract

While there is a growing body of scholarship on the neoliberal content of global English textbooks, the ways in which these commercial materials come to life in teaching and learning practices are still under researched. Drawing on a critical ethnographic account of two English courses for unemployed students in a private language school in Serbia, this paper examines the beliefs and actions of teachers and students in regard to English language education and the global textbooks they use. The results suggest that many views about the English language courses and their textbooks in this case study are deeply shaped by the broader socioeconomic context of neoliberalism. Furthermore, the neoliberalism featured in the textbook motivates students to learn English and to transform themselves into suitable citizens and workers for the current economic order. In this way, the global textbook becomes one of the many tools that neoliberalism uses to reproduce itself. This paper argues that the present state of affairs is not an inevitable and desirable one and calls for implementing alternative approaches to the dominant neoliberal conception of English language education.

Keywords: English language education; neoliberalism; global English textbooks; critical ethnography; Serbia

1. Introduction

Capitalism, in its neoliberal form, has infiltrated all spheres of our contemporary lives, from political economy and international trade (Harvey 2005) to the ways in which people relate with others and how we present ourselves (Rose 1999; Dardot and Laval 2013). One of the areas that is most affected by neoliberalism is education (Hill and Kumar 2009), which includes language learning and teaching (Bernstein et al 2015). Although critical studies of

the global spread of English started to surface in the 1990s (e.g. Phillipson 1992), only in the past few years has the attention focused on the different levels of impact that neoliberalism had in the particular field of English Language Teaching (ELT).

The most evident neoliberal effect in ELT is the extended conception of the language purely as a job skill or as a tool for economic success (Kubota 2011; Shin 2016). This newly heightened conception of English learning reflects the human capital theory (Becker 1962), a cornerstone of the neoliberal ideology which sustains that what is done and what is learned must be measured in accordance to the economic benefits that can be achieved. According to this theory, education is an investment made by individuals (and states) to improve their productivity. Human capital principles encourage learners to become self-regulating subjects who are continuously developing their own capabilities to meet the demands of the market. In this context, states all around the world, supranational organizations and private corporations promote the utilitarian necessity to learn English skills to foster the competitiveness of both countries and individuals (Price 2014). Consequently, many people across the globe are incited to learn a foreign language, especially English, “to seek global career opportunities and to develop a competitive edge in increasingly uncertain employment conditions under neoliberalism” (Kubota 2016: 468-469). Park (2016) illustrates this point with what he calls ‘the ideology of language as pure potential’ in the context of the ‘Korean English fever’. English learners in South Korea seek (and are forced by the neoliberal climate) to invest in learning English skills in order to improve their chances of getting a better job (Park 2016). However, the valorization of English as a crucial aspect for professional and personal success under neoliberalism collides with reality. As Park and Lo (2012: 157) indicate “English language skills alone are rarely considered to be sufficient in marking the speaker as a valued individual in the global economy”. Actually, rewarding personal investment in language learning with profit “is far from coming about automatically for everyone” (Flubacher et al.

2017: 2), as structural inequalities based on social class, geographical location, gender and race play a more important role (Kubota 2011). In addition, to find a good job, the general economic situation is also crucial: “Employment rates go up and overall earnings fall because of developments in the economy which impact on the labour market, irrespective of what skills potential workers are gaining” (Holborow 2018: 523).

An increasing focus of research about the impact of neoliberalism in language education has been on the content of the language textbooks, especially for learning English (e.g. Chun 2009; Gray 2012; Copley 2018), but also French (Block and Gray 2018), Spanish (Bori and Kuzmanović-Jovanović 2020 forthcoming; Bori and Kuzmanović-Jovanović 2021 forthcoming), and Catalan (Bori 2018). This growing body of research has opened venues for new critical perspectives that could challenge the current hegemony of neoliberalism in language education. However, this scholarship contains an important gap and that is the examination of the ways in which neoliberal textbooks come to life in the classroom. This paper aims to fill this gap by drawing on a critical ethnographic account of English courses in a private language school in Serbia that use global textbooks. In particular, I attempt to illustrate the ways in which questions of power and knowledge are articulated by the main actors of these courses in relation to English education and the global textbook. In doing so, I will address the relations between the participants’ perspectives at a micro level and the broader economic, political and social conditions of neoliberal capitalism.

I begin this article by discussing the impact of neoliberalism in global ELT textbooks. The next section situates this study in the framework of critical ethnography and explains how the analysis is developed. The following section outlines the results of the study, which are later discussed against the backdrop of neoliberalism. I conclude the paper by considering the particular implications of my findings for language education and suggesting future directions for research.

2. Neoliberalism in global ELT textbooks

In recent years, a growing body of research has made important efforts in documenting neoliberal features found in the content of global ELT materials. In his critical study of an English for Academic Purposes program at a US university, Chun (2009) indicates that the materials used in the classroom are based on neoliberal discourses of entrepreneurialism and constant self-improvement. Gray (2010a, 2010b, 2012) shows that global ELT textbooks embody many neoliberal values such as individualism, aspiration, affluence, consumerism, self-branding and mobility. Elsewhere, Gray and Block (2014) and Copley (2018) converge to highlight the shift in the content of global ELT textbooks since the 1990s from collective issues to an extreme individualism, coinciding with the rise of neoliberalism as the dominant ideological paradigm.

Drawing on detailed critical discourse analysis, two other recent studies make even more visible the neoliberal ethos of ELT textbooks. Xiong and Yuan (2018) uncover textbooks' promotion of English as capital and of an individualistic language learning, while Babaii and Sheiki (2018) illustrate the popularization of a market-driven society and consumerism to mention but a few of the neoliberal tenets found in these commercial language materials. Along these lines of research, Bori (2020) goes a step further arguing that global ELT textbooks not only inscribe neoliberal meanings to the language taught, as explained by the previously mentioned studies but, moreover, they may shape the conduct of the learners in accordance to free-market values and practices.

Furthermore, it is also necessary to stress that commercial language materials are a key component of the huge profits generated by the massive ELT industry within neoliberal globalization. The main beneficiaries of this business are major British and North-American publishing houses, which constantly fill the global ELT market with new teaching materials

(Barnawi 2018:16). Global ELT textbooks are frequently introduced in many countries with aggressive marketing campaigns to compete with locally produced materials (Gray 2010b: 716).

The case of Serbia is illustrative of the ways in which global ELT textbooks have become widely-used in many parts of the world. During the period of socialist Yugoslavia, the country had a solid state textbook industry, which more recently entered into a crisis with the liberalization of the textbook market and the consequent influx of foreign publishers' educational materials. A few years ago there was even a public debate about it. Some teachers stood against it, while others sustained that it would be beneficial to open the country in this way to international trends and advances. Lobbies from foreign publishing houses also took part in the debate and, in the end, the free market supporters won. In consequence, many international textbooks are used today not only in private schools but also in public education, as the Serbian Ministry of Education includes several of them in the list of textbooks recommended for state schools.

3. Critical ethnography

Critical ethnography aims to understand a particular social setting through the analysis of what the actors involved say, do or think. It requires fieldwork in situ for a longer period of time, the collection of data (participant's observation, interviews, etc.) and their interpretation, normally through a qualitative approach. What differentiates critical ethnography from traditional ethnographic studies is its explicit political purpose (Talmy 2013). Drawing on one or more of the traditions of critical theory (Kinchloe and McLaren 2005), critical ethnographers are involved in issues of inequality, power relations and hegemony "in order to potentially foster social change in direct or indirect ways" (Palmer and Caldas 2017: 382). Despite its enormous potential to "penetrate hidden meanings and

underlying connections” between language classrooms and the broader political, social and economic context (Kumaravadivelu 1999: 476), very few studies have examined ELT courses and its commercial materials through the lens of critical ethnography. The only known critical ethnographic research about ELT textbooks in actual classes was published over 25 years ago by Canagarajah (1993). He suggested that Tamil learners in Sri Lanka developed various forms of resistance against the communicative ELT approach and the cultures presented in the Western produced textbook used in the classroom, which were very far from the reality and the tradition of this specific context.

In what follows, I present the broader context and the particular setting of my critical ethnographic study, as well as the research questions, the data collection and the procedures of analysis.

3.1 Serbian context

After a decade of devastating wars, crippling international sanctions and hyperinflation in the 1990s, Serbia effectively began its transformation from socialism to capitalism in 2000, with mass privatizations of public companies and the deregulation of its economy under the guidance of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank (WB). Despite the public’s high expectations at the end of this isolation, the level of economic and social conditions of the former epoch of Yugoslavia has never been restored. Many national industries have collapsed and the public sector has been seriously weakened, while foreign-owned companies and certain local oligarchies have made fortunes in the process of privatization. As a consequence, thousands of jobs have been destroyed and low salaries barely allow families to make ends meet. Although the state still controls some (increasingly fewer) strategic economic sectors, Serbia is now in practice incorporated into the free market economy from a peripheral position. This indeed means an almost total economic

dependence on the capitalist core and its multinational banks and corporations (Horvat and Štiks 2012), while the IMF and the WB continue to play a key role in its economic policies. Many Serbian people feel economically robbed by the privatization process and helpless and vulnerable in the face of the state, especially if they compare the current situation with their parents' realities in the past under a socialist regime. Despite reoccurring domestic economic crises, this larger shift to a free market economy has been sustained by a strong public discourse disseminated by political elites, mainstream media and NGOs that justify neoliberal reforms as a 'moral project' for the good of society (Mikuš 2016).

3.2 The setting

Serbia is a country with a long and strong tradition of foreign language teaching, English being the most common foreign language taught both in formal and informal education in recent decades (Filipović et al. 2007). The fieldwork for this study took place in one of the best-known private language schools in Belgrade over four months (November 2018-February 2019). I observed two courses of English for general purposes of Elementary and Pre-intermediate level. The first one had 4 students and the other one 7 students. Learners (8 women and 3 men) were between 28 and 42 years old. All of them had completed higher education and were unemployed. They enrolled in the language school through the State Unemployment Agency with a 70% discount on the standard price of the course. A global ELT textbook, published by Cambridge University Press, was the main material used in the classroom. As stated in the previous section, global ELT textbooks are used not only in private language academies but also in many primary and secondary public schools in Serbia. The particular setting was chosen for this study because it corresponds with the specific profile of students, i.e. unemployed people encouraged by the State and the overall neoliberal climate to learn English to improve their employability. The classes observed covered four

out of twelve units of the global ELT textbook. One of the courses followed *Face2Face/Elementary* while the other one used *Face2Face/Pre-Intermediate*. Each class was developed in accordance to the structure and the contents of the global textbook. Very few extra materials were used in the classroom. The only extra teachers' explanations were about grammatical aspects. The textbook thus was the de facto curriculum of the course, as is often the case in many other language classrooms around the world (Guerrettaz and Johnston 2013).

3.3 Research questions

The critical ethnographic study was guided by three research questions:

1. How is the English language course conceived by the teachers and the language school and what are the students' motivations and expectations in learning English?
2. Does the content presented in the global ELT textbooks differ from the lived reality of the participants of this study and, if so, how?
3. What are participants' perceptions of the global ELT textbooks?

These questions provide us the necessary data to analyze how neoliberalism affects the language learning process. The teachers' and students' perspectives about their language teaching and learning, their proper analysis of the content of textbooks compared with their lived reality and their perceptions of global ELT textbooks all help to provide an understanding of how neoliberalism shapes their lives and attitudes while teaching and learning English.

3.4 Data collection

Before starting the fieldwork, a first approximation to the case study was conducted. On the one hand, I analyzed the neoliberal content of the global ELT textbooks used in the courses.

A part of the results of this examination is explained with certain detail elsewhere (Bori 2020). On the other hand, I examined the discourses that the language school uses for promoting itself on its website. I began my fieldwork with non-participant observation in both courses. The classes took place two times per week, and each session lasted for 90 minutes. Towards the end of the courses, I conducted semi-structured interviews with the learners. I interviewed 7 out of 11 students. Three of the students declined my invitation because they did not have time for it, while another one quit the course before I started the interviews. In these face-to-face interviews with learners that lasted between 30 and 50 minutes, the researcher followed the same lines of questioning for each student and allowed participants to address other related topics if they liked. Interviews were centered on issues related to: (a) the participant's personal, social and economic background; (b) motivations and expectations for learning English; and (c) perceptions of the language textbook.

Around the same time, interviews were carried out with the teachers of the two courses. Both of them come from Serbia and have degrees in English Language and Literature. They are between 28 and 32 years old and have more than 4 years of experience in ELT. Their interviews were closely modeled on the same topics addressed in the students' interviews and lasted around one hour. Finally, an interview was conducted with another teacher, the language school's head of studies. This last interview took about 30 minutes and dealt with general considerations about the selection of the textbooks and the organization of the English courses. While the interviews with the two teachers of the courses were conducted in English, the rest were in Serbian and the quotations in the paper are my own English translations. All names of the interviewees mentioned are pseudonyms.

3.5 Analysis procedures

After reading my field notes of the classroom observation and examining the interview transcripts, the discourses of the textbooks and of the school language website, I used an

inductive approach to answer the three research questions, by identifying emerging patterns and topics that arose from the data collected. Then, in keeping with the Student et al. (2017: 594) ethnographic approach, the findings are discussed by relating them to “the forces of history and the society” in which participants live. In other words, the results are considered in light of the relationship between neoliberalism on the one hand and ELT and the textbook on the other.

4. Results

4.1 Motivations and expectations

On its website, the school tags language learning as an indispensable tool for personal and professional development: “the high school diploma is no longer enough to get a job.

Working on yourself has become necessary”. The website also informs potential students that “there are more and more companies that do business all over the world, but this would not be possible if they did not hire people who think globally and speak at least one foreign language”. Furthermore, the website advertises the school with the following argument: “Learning foreign languages opens the doors to many career possibilities. This is not related only to the possibilities of working part-time or at outsourcing jobs, although these are excellent reasons”.

The head of studies of the school recognizes that “unfortunately” language learning indeed is a product that people buy and “advertising is a crucial factor for language schools in times of competence” (Interview, 5/06/2019). Both teachers also consider that the language school is selling a commodity, although they do not consider this a natural and a desirable conception, but it is the current state of affairs that imposes it: “Well, sadly, we live in a consumer society. I think that it’s like this in every school. Everybody does it. I mean, the school is indeed selling a product” (Interview, Jasmina, 03/03/2019).

All students in this case study have spent many years learning English during the course of their state education, but they are not satisfied with their language competences. They believe that private schools have better means and methods than state school education to get them to the level of English they need. In this sense, Mina explains:

I studied English in primary school, high school and at the university [laughter], but it wasn't good enough, so now I want to learn it better. Here [in the private school] is where I started speaking for the first time and understanding everything (Interview, 5/02/2019).

Indeed, there is a demand from employers for a certain level of English in order to apply for almost any skilled job in Serbia, so unemployed people are bound to enhance their English language proficiency. In this regard, all students stated that they were studying English especially in order to find a better job. Viktor, who has recently started to work as a part-time interviewer for a State Survey Agency, explains it in the following way:

Me: Why do you study English?

Viktor: Well, because it's the most needed language today, it is considered to be a kind of basic language for everything, for business or other... One needs English in every instance.

Me: But why do *you* need it?

Viktor: I don't need English that much for the current job that I have, but I will, especially for future jobs since I don't plan to do this all my life (Interview, 13/02/2019).

On the other hand, Ana, who has a degree in geography, explains that she learns English for the perceived needs of the company where she wants to work in the immediate future:

The company works exclusively with English speaking countries. It offers technical support. This particular company works for Amazon: dealing with complaints, petitions, tracking the packages... So, I need it for work. On the other hand, I'm learning English because in the near future, in the next three or four years, I want to move out of the country (Interview, 6/02/2019).

Another common feature in the student's answers is that they would work in improving their English, even if they had a well-paid job. Indeed, students believe that they should always improve themselves in all spheres of their lives. Katarina, for example, says:

I think that everyone should be independent. Here in Serbia this is difficult, because children live with their parents until they turn 30 or 35, and this is considered normal, while in some other countries young people from 18 and into their 20s leave home and become financially independent. I think everyone should try to do one's best. This is definitely very important. We should always strive for the best (Interview, 15/02/2019).

4.2 Opposite realities

To answer the second research question, I examined the relationship between the content presented in textbooks and the lived reality of the students outside of the classroom. Like many current global ELT textbooks (Gray and Block 2014), *Face2Face* prioritizes the lifestyle of the upper-middle class in its texts and activities. Most of the situations presented concern business-related topics, the pastimes of people without economic limitations, and travel to far destinations. The pictures accompanying the texts feature mostly smartly dressed men and women, smiling, various products to consume and spectacular landscapes. This privileged reality in textbooks contrasts sharply with the lived reality of unemployed students in Serbia. Ana, a 42-year-old mother, illustrated her living conditions with the following comment in the Serbian language to her classmates:

This morning I've gone to buy cleaning products in a supermarket on the other side of the city. It's much cheaper than in the other places. I've spent a great deal of time, but it's worth it. I always do that with our shopping. I search the whole city to find cheaper products. If I can save some money with cleaning products, then with the food, and with the clothes, at the end of the month we save a small amount that means

a lot to us. We live, you know, four people, only on the modest wages of my husband (Field notes, Pre-intermediate class, 17/12/2018).

The thin connection between the reality of ELT textbooks and the life of students is particularly evident when the content deals with consumption practices. In one of the activities, for example, students worked in pairs to ask each other questions suggested by the textbooks, such as the following:

How do you usually pay for meals in a restaurant?

Ana: In cash. But I don't go to restaurants. I don't have a credit card.

Viktor: Me neither.

Ana: I don't have a job.

Viktor: I go to a students' cantina to eat. I have no money to go to a restaurant.

Similar answers could be heard to the same question in the other pairs of students.

(Field notes, Pre-intermediate class, 10/12/2018)

The contrast between the content of the textbooks and students' real life was also manifested when dealing with texts about journeys to far destinations and expensive travel arrangements.

An extract from field notes during one class dedicated to this topic illustrates this point:

After doing a speaking exercise proposed by the textbook to summarize a text about an unusual hotel in Chile with rooms that costs \$180 a night, one of the students, Katarina, adds a final comment: "But it's very expensive". And the teacher says: "Too expensive, I would say". Some of the students nod in consent (Field notes, Pre-intermediate class, 09/01/2019).

4.3 Perceptions of the textbook

The third research question addresses the participants' perceptions of the global ELT textbooks used in the classrooms. As seen above, the textbooks represent an idealized view of the world that collides with the immediate experiences of the students. Most of them explained that successful lives of rich people featured in textbooks encourage them to learn English.

Me: Does this story of a successful businesswoman that appears in the textbook motivate you to learn English?

Marija: Yes, this lesson motivates me. It is a good thing that she is a businesswoman. It motivates me, of course.

Me: Why?

Marija: Well, because we all want to see positive things. Success. I don't have ambitions to become a businesswoman like her. I mean, I do wish to work in a company like her, but not to be a CEO, but, okay, maybe yes, one day [laughter] (Interview, 5/02/2019).

When commenting on the travel and hotels featured in textbooks affordable only for rich people, Katarina explains that this content gives her goals and direction to move forward in life.

Me: Do you enjoy seeing content in the textbooks related to the lifestyles of wealthy people, such as expensive travel or luxury hotels?

Katarina: Well, okay, when there is this kind of text about powerful people with more money, I think, it can be motivation in a sense. I'll learn new vocabulary, the texts are interesting, and it's great because you never know how far you can get, what can happen. [...] I always say okay, now I'm going to improve myself, I'm going to be better, I'm going to learn and this will perhaps allow me to have a better job, maybe I'll be the one to go to that luxury hotel (Interview, 15/02/2019).

However, other answers show that the neoliberal promises presented in textbooks pose tensions among some participants. The comments by Viktor about the content related to travels to far away destinations in textbooks are emblematic of the conflicts that this content generates in some students:

Viktor: I, for example, didn't travel at all last year, and, it bothers me a little... It's okay to travel, but now it's normal to travel all the time ... Now we all should travel so much, and what if we can't? Well, I would be more interested in foreign cultures, not so much in exotic places, some of which are not possible for the majority, especially for us who come from the Unemployment Agency [laughter].

Me: Why does this kind of content bother you?

Viktor: Because rich people are in the minority. There aren't that many of them, and they are the ones that appear most, as if they are the only ones that exist. Also, because other people shouldn't be neglected (Interview, 13/02/2019).

One of the texts that both students and the teacher recognized influenced their worldviews and even, in some cases, their own plans for the future was about a couple that lost their jobs. They decided to live in a boat and move constantly to wherever they could find work (Redston and Cunningham 2012: 63). Although the characters were forced to live in a boat due to their unemployment, they love this new way of life. The daily difficulties of living in a tiny space, moving from one place to another or looking for a new job are not mentioned. The unemployed students, who mostly live with their parents or in small flats in the suburbs, explained that this story inspired them to think about trying out this lifestyle in the future.

Nikola: This lesson was very refreshing. It reminded me of freedom. It made me think.

Me: How?

Nikola: I'm planning to buy a caravan this year for my family. I've been following a couple on Instagram that travels like this. Their web site is called 'where is my office now?' Very interesting. They travel and live in a van and have been doing it for six years. This was my favorite unit (Interview, 5/02/2019).

Another point that emerged from the data is the students' and teachers' agreement that business-related content in the ELT classroom is necessary and beneficial. Global textbooks propose activities to guide students to find a new job, teaching them how to read job advertisements, to write CVs and cover letters or how to behave in a job interview. These activities were conducted in full in the classroom. When I asked one of the teachers why she insisted so much on these kinds of activities, she explained:

I think it can be helpful because we analyze what a job advert looks like, how they would read it, what their opinion is, I mean, if they would like to do this kind of job or not. Then, we move on to the cover letter. I always make some kind of connection between the cover letter they might want to write for themselves and then I point out a couple of things that might be useful for them [...] when they apply for a job (Interview, Jasmina, 03/03/2019).

When asked about the possibility of using an ELT textbook in the classroom that was written in Serbia, the head of studies rejected this idea because, according to her, local textbooks are old fashioned with respect to their topics and teaching methodologies. On the other hand, both teachers explained that it might be interesting as students would be able to relate more easily to local issues, although they added that they had never worked with a textbook that was not from the UK or USA. However, most of the students explained that they prefer using a global ELT textbook over a local one, although none of them remembered ever having seen a Serbian ELT textbook. Students stated that the fact that the authors are native speakers gave them a guarantee of quality.

5. Discussion

5.1. Neoliberal capitalism vs. socialism

Many views about ELT and its global textbooks in this case study are deeply shaped by the broader socioeconomic context of neoliberalism. The most pronounced one is that the very reason for learning this language is to get a good job. Students, teachers and the school's website articulate it following the neoliberal conception of English as human capital which sustains that there is a natural bond between finding a better job and knowing English. It is true, though, that students sometimes state that third parties (i.e. their future employers) are the ones asking for English. Another preconception related to learning English is the student's belief that private schools have better methods to teach the language than the public

education, which is also aligned with the dominant neoliberal discourse that disdains the public and praises everything private.

The jobs aspired to by these students are the result of the neoliberal economic reforms in Serbia in the last two decades. The school's website highlights outsourcing jobs as good professional opportunities for the students. In this connection, Ana, who has a degree in geography, says that she would like to work for a call center which provides services to an English-speaking market. This mismatch between people's university qualifications and their jobs is one of the salient features of the neoliberal work order (Kalleberg 2007). As in the socialist period, Serbia still educates a high percentage of university graduates. What is new now is that the system does not provide a job to these people after completing their studies. A couple of decades ago, Ana would probably experience a quick transition from school to a job related to her studies. It is also interesting to note here the specific Serbian context and the desperate situation of its population. Being an agent in a call center is regarded by university-educated people in Western countries as a failure since this job does not meet the expectations of middle-class distinction of the individuals and their parents (Matos 2012). By contrast, in Serbia it is often considered as upward social mobility because, in the face of the recent years of war and the current shortage of work, this job is regarded as an attractive option taking into consideration that its salary is often higher than the average wage (van der Naald 2016).

Another characteristic of the neoliberal work order that affects students' perceptions is the constant change of jobs. Many of them do not plan to do the same job all of their lives, unlike their parents and grandparents who lived in times of full and stable employment. English, according to students, can help them in that. A better life for some of them means moving to another country, a practice also tightly linked to neoliberal globalization, with the constant movement of people, goods and services (Harvey 2005). Before, in the times of socialism,

most people who left the country had little formal education and worked in low-skilled jobs abroad, while most university-educated people stayed in the country permanently as they could easily find a job in their field. Nowadays many highly qualified young professionals are leaving the country in search of better living conditions. Quite a few of them work in low-skilled and casual jobs, although they are likely to be paid three times as much in some Western countries than in Serbia.

The selection of global textbooks, over locally produced ones, is also an effect of the neoliberal reforms undertaken in Serbia in the past few decades, with the liberalization of the textbooks' market and the consequent weakening of state publishing houses. It should be noted that none of the teachers and students remembered having ever used a local ELT textbook, which is indicative of the current widespread presence of the global ELT materials in Serbia.

5.2 Aspirational content

Data indicate that the idealized content presented in global textbooks has little, if anything, to do with the lives of the participants of this study. The ELT industry refers to this content as 'aspirational', meaning that the reality centered on consumerism, professional and personal success, and travel featured in textbooks represents the kind of life that most language students aspire to and therefore interests them and motivates them to learn English (Gray 2010a). Many of the students' answers confirm this ELT industry assumption. It could be argued that ELT textbook's aspirational content might contribute toward hiding the structural inequalities of neoliberal societies by presenting an idealized reality and therefore reinforce the existent social order. This dominant trend in textbooks, however, is not exempt from conflicts, as some participants are aware of the gap between what neoliberal textbooks present and how the real world works. This awareness of the distortions of the neoliberal

fantasy might open ways to undermine its hegemony (Holborow 2015). Yet, the fact that neither any activity in the classroom nor any of the participants' comments openly challenged neoliberal ideology shows that neoliberalism is stronger than the little sparks of resistance to the textbooks' neoliberal content identified in this study, such as the comments by Viktor about travels to far away destinations.

5.3 Self-responsibilization

The results show that students think that they should always try to be better in everything they do, including mastering English to improve their chances of getting a job. For them, as for many English students around the world (Park and Lo 2012; Shin 2016), learning English is essentially an individual project of self-improvement which increases their individual chances to succeed in life. In that way, participants in this case study have succumbed to the predominant rhetoric which follows the hegemonic neoliberal discourse in proclaiming that every one of us should bear responsibility for our own destiny, becoming entrepreneurs of ourselves and, as such, assume risks and develop the skills required by the market (Dardot and Laval 2013).

Since students and teachers see the current socioeconomic situation as inevitable, they try to blend into this new economic, political and social order, accepting the neoliberal narratives of meritocracy, self-responsibility and self-branding. This point is illustrated by their ideas about the imperative need to learn business-related content in ELT. This kind of textbook content addresses students as entrepreneurial selves, who should read the job market and learn how to present themselves in order to be attractive to potential employers. In this particular instance, the textbook, together with the additional explanations of the teachers and the learners' efforts to perform the textbook's activities well, plays an important role in

modeling the students' conduct to discipline themselves according to the neoliberal principles of flexibility, competition and self-responsibility.

Meanwhile, texts that encourage individual freedom and personal choices place students within the neoliberal way of acting guided by freedom, understood as "the capacity to realize one's desires in one's secular life, to fulfill one's potential through one's own endeavours, to determine the course of one's own existence through acts of choice" (Rose 1999: 84).

According to students' answers, the goal of their learning the English language is inspired by certain social and life skills that will make them autonomous individuals primarily driven by freedom of choice, self-fulfillment, and economic self-reliance.

5.4 The need for critical pedagogy

Students and teachers in this case study mostly accept neoliberalism as a norm, and even though they sometimes state their objections, they feel powerless about it. A crucial task for critical scholars is therefore to raise consciousness about the need to challenge neoliberal tenets in language classrooms. This might be achieved by giving a critical direction to language course programs and above all by making critical pedagogy the foundation of future language teachers' curriculums. The focus on the "relationships between language learning and social change" (Norton and Toohey 2004: 1) could certainly help future teachers to become critically aware citizens, who are mindful that language education is shaped by a greater socioeconomic context. It would also be advisable to open public discussions on this issue among institutions and organizations dealing with language education. It is worth noting that the current neoliberal orientation of language education is not the only one possible, as shown in the alternative approach developed in Uruguay in the 2000s. The left-wing government of that time advocated a discursive change in the orientation of English language education: from English as a tool for economic development in the global market

towards “a tool for empowerment that enables citizens to transform current (hegemonic) practices” (Canale 2015: 36).

ELT teachers and institutions interested in applying critical approaches to neoliberalism could refocus language courses to allow students to develop critical awareness, offering spaces in the classroom to reflect upon and question widespread neoliberal assumptions about language learning. The ways in which this critical approach is to be developed in the classroom should necessarily vary depending on the local context and its broader educational, social and cultural values. In our case study, teachers could have avoided some of the content in global textbooks which is alien to the participants’ background and, instead, introduce classroom materials with meaningful and thought-provoking topics for students. Moreover, the teachers could have made greater use of the students’ own moments of critical awareness, such as those offered by Viktor, Ana, and Katarina, to encourage discussion about controversial issues in the classroom.

Alternatively, language schools might explore the possibility of using other materials in the classroom, such as locally produced textbooks which could potentially encourage a different kind of approach than the one proposed by the global textbook, more sensitive to the needs of the local culture.

Another suggestion could be using a textbook addressed to a global audience with an overtly critical perspective. An example of such material is a textbook from Iran called *Alternative View* (Abdelrahim 2012), which draws on the problem-posing approach whereby students are stimulated through open questions to think about a wide range of global issues (stereotypes, drug addiction, the media, sports, terrorism, democracy, technology, etc.). For example, in one unit devoted to English as a global language, students are encouraged to discuss this topic with thought-provoking questions that can help them raise their critical consciousness, such as in the following passage:

What's the link between American hegemony and English language? What's mcdonaldization and how is related to English? How do books like Interchange [a famous commercial global ELT textbook] aid in the mcdonaldization process? What does it mean to teach for a different world? (Abdelrahim 2012: 12).

In my view, people interested in applying critical approaches in language education have much to learn from this kind of material. What now remains is to encourage all the participants in the language learning process to be conscious of the need to question the dominant neoliberal conception of language education.

6. Conclusions

This paper suggests that participants' beliefs and actions in this case study are the result of the wider neoliberal context of Serbia. Neoliberalism appears here as an external force imposed on participants by the political and economic climate in various ways. First, students are required to conceive English as human capital, that is, as a tool to fit better into the new work order. Their potential employers and the State Unemployment Agency are the ones asking these unemployed students to learn English to foster their competitiveness, and not the other way around. Second, participants do not have the opportunity to use a local ELT textbook in the classroom, because of the liberalization of the textbook market and the resultant dominance of foreign educational products. It should be stressed that participants have mostly stated they are against locally produced textbooks, biased by the powerful propaganda of the global ELT industry, which favors native speakers and UK/US produced textbooks as the major authority in language education.

The results indicate that the idealized reality featured in the global textbook contrasts sharply with the precarious living conditions of the students. However, the textbook still has the force to reproduce and to enlarge the dominant set of values circulating in the society, by

presenting neoliberal promises as something that motivates students to learn English and to transform themselves into suitable citizens and workers for today's economy. It would thus appear that the prevailing values and beliefs of the wider society, reinforced partly by the central role the global textbook plays in the classroom, cause neoliberalism to emerge here as the only horizon possible for participants, which undermines any collective and transformative project.

Yet, some responses from interviewees and the contrast between today's neoliberal society and the recent Serbian socialist past show that the current state of affairs is not a natural, inevitable and desirable one. There is thus still room to challenge the ways in which neoliberalism shapes ELT and its textbooks, as long as we make obvious to the greatest number of people possible the need to challenge the present situation and to inspire others to change their thinking on neoliberal language education. What is most important above all is to establish critical pedagogy as the basis of language teacher training courses. In this way, several alternatives to current neoliberal language education could be put forward, such as redesigning language courses to encourage students to think outside the box and using different classroom materials which provide content more relevant and more intellectually stimulating for learners than the commercial global ELT textbooks.

Lastly, future ethnographic studies are needed in order to continue to approach widely-disseminated forms of knowledge and beliefs in ELT and to understand, when it occurs, the reasons why teachers and learners interiorize neoliberalism in their personal convictions and acts. With such critical reflections inside the classrooms and in our fields of research, we would finally be able to raise awareness of the need to free ourselves from "the grip of neoliberalism" (Park 2016: 463) under which we live.

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